

GLUED LAMINATED BAMBOO PANELS FOR ARCHITECTURAL COMPONENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports a scientific initiation research on glue laminated bamboo panels, or engineered bamboo, using a polymeric biodegradable adhesive based on *mamona* oil, with a view to producing prototypes to get tectonic, eco-efficient and renewable architectural components. It was used the *Dendrocalamus Asper* bamboo culms from clumps existing in the Northeast Region of Brazil. Considering the importance of sealing systems for the delimitation of architectural spaces and the environmental impact caused by conventional masonry systems, floors and roofs, the investigation on glued laminated bamboo as a renewable and expressive material in these systems need to be deepened.

KEYWORDS

Glue laminated bamboo; biodegradable polymeric adhesives; eco-efficient sealing systems.

INTRODUCTION

Understanding that sustainability is an indispensable theme for the design of contemporary architecture, buildings with bamboo appear as an alternative to conventional construction methods. As a renewable material and biological resource, with low energy cost, ecologically correct and economically viable, mainly in developing countries like Brazil, bamboo also has great technical and expressive potential and can enhance the tectonic character of architecture when used in delimiting components of the architectural space, such as: structure, walls, ceilings, floors, among others. The effective use of these bamboo components by the construction industry requires their production on an industrial scale, as it already occurs in developed countries as China and Japan, but it must be increased in our country, given the predominance of the tropical climate and large extension of land suitable for plantations of species of bamboo appropriate for this purpose. Otherwise, the entire Brazil's territory is within the global extension more suitable for the cultivation of bamboo in its various species (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Bamboo distribution map in the world. Edited by authors. Source: Jaime Baladrón Laborda.

Due to these advantages, the interest in bamboo in Brazil has been growing, given the number of research in universities visualizing the favouring of a large-scale production and boosting its various forms of use. One of them is the use of bamboo in the form of pressed panels. Glued laminated bamboo, as it is named, or engineered bamboo, is made up of strips extracted from the culms, planed, and glued together. One of the possibilities of using glued laminated bamboo, is in the conformation of vertical closures, which can be designed and executed in different ways, with different construction techniques (MOIZES, 2007).

This paper reports the result of a scientific initiation research on glue laminated bamboo panels, or engineered bamboo, using adhesives based on biodegradable polymers, with a view to producing prototypes to get tectonic, eco-efficient and renewable architectural components.

The research was carried out at the Federal University of Paraíba located in the northeaster of Brazil, in one of the poorest states of the country from an economic point of view, but that presents propitious climate conditions for the cultivation of bamboo in the "Cariri", "Brejo" and coastal regions of it, such as the *Bambusa vulgaris*, the *Dendrocalamus asper*, the *Bambusa tuldoides*, the *Guadua angustifolia*, among others.

As part of the studies carried out by the research group "Tectonics and Sustainability in Architecture - TEKTONIK.AS - the research reported here has two broader objectives: to introduce the principles of sustainability in the design learning process of architecture, engineering and design students viewing to inserting the project in an eco-responsible context, seeking answers to social, environmental and economic questions; and to encourage the bamboo production chain in the State of Paraíba, since it appears as an eco-efficient and renewable alternative, which can increase the bioeconomy sector in that state.

The investigation began by reviewing the literature on bamboo lamination processes and techniques and on biodegradable polymeric adhesives. The next step consisted on extracted *Dendrocalamus Asper* bamboo culms from clumps existing in our state, located in the Northeast Region of Brazil. Afterwards, the slats extracted from the culms were treated in an autoclave, immersed in a solution of boric acid and borax, and subsequently dried in a kiln. The bamboo battens were processed, then glued and pressed using a polymeric biodegradable adhesive based on *mamona* oil (castor resin). Then, testing was made to verify the mechanical performance - its resistance to compression and shear efforts - permitting a comparative analysis of the results obtained with those studied in the literature. The last stage of the research consisted of the design of a partition wall for the architectural space made up of glued laminated bamboo panels, and a prototype was also carried out. In conclusion, it was possible to verify the advantages and qualities of bamboo as a renewable raw material, achieving very significant mechanical resistance results, as well as a nice aesthetic which can enhance the tectonic character of the architecture.

This paper reports the results of the research in three parts, from the harvesting and laminating of the culms, the mechanical tests, the design, and realization of the prototype, ending with the conclusions.

FROM HARVEST TO CULMS LAMINATION

In the investigation of the literature on Glued Laminated Bamboo (GLB), the study of the most suitable species for the purposes set out in this research, the treatment and lamination processes, was prioritized, selecting works that guide their practical application. Thus, based on this literary review, the species selected for the study was *Dendrocalamus Asper*, a clumping bamboo with stalk height that can reach 30 meters and a diameter that can reach 20 centimetres. The thickness of the culm wall of this bamboo species can reach about 2.5 centimetres, which facilitates the manufacture of slats to produce GLB, as explained by Shrestha & Crews (2014) and Boogard (2016). In addition, *Dendrocalamus Asper* develops well in tropical regions, both in hot-humid and hot-dry climates, characteristic of regions of Paraíba.

After selecting the species, culms were extracted from existing clumps on Campus II of the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), in the city of Areia located in the Brejo region of Paraíba.

Harvesting the culms followed the recommendation of Pereira and Beraldo (2016) for clumping species: choose the most mature bamboos, which have white spots, cut 20 centimetres from the ground and above the node to prevent the remaining culm from rotting with the entry of water (Figure 2). The bamboo culms were cut with the aid of an electric saw measuring approximately 1.5 meters to

facilitate transport to the Laboratory of Materials and Structures Tests (LABEME), located on Campus I, in the city of João Pessoa.

Figure 2: Extraction of culms in the tussock.

Process of treatment and lamination

Although bamboo is a material with high mechanical strength (BOOGARD, 2016), its durability under natural conditions is approximately 2 (two) years due to some variables such as the presence of starch. According to Rivero (2003) and Beraldo (2019), the presence of starch is proven to be the weak point of bamboo, as it is related to the attack of woodworm (*Dinoderus minutus*), and most bamboo species have low natural durability when attack by xylophagous organisms. Thus, regardless of the bamboo species used, the treatment of the culms is essential to ensure greater durability, being the next step after its extraction.

It was decided to treat the bamboos in two ways, for later comparison of results. The first type of treatment used was chemical, also by immersion of the stems in water, however, adding boric acid and borax (Octoborate), and using one as performed by Rosa (2013) in her work. In this type of treatment, an autoclave was used to accelerate the process in which the slats were left for a period of 24 hours at a temperature of 90 degrees (Figure 4). It was necessary to section the culms in the form of slats, with the aid of a circular saw and cut into lengths of 35 and 40 centimeters to fit the specific dimensions of the equipment available in the laboratory (Figure 3). To fully immerse the slats in the autoclave, 58 liters of water were needed and, according to the manufacturer, the concentration of boric acid and borax should be 3%, then 1.74 kg of each reagent were added. The second type was made in naturally way, by immersion in water for seven days, a treatment that provides the reduction or elimination of starch (RIVERO, 2003 and BERALDO, 2019).

Figure 3: Cutting the culms to obtain the slats.

Figure 4: Water-soluble treatment in autoclave

After the two types of immersion treatment, the next step was drying the culms and slats, with the support of greenhouses to accelerate the process. In the treatment using only water, a greenhouse was used where the culms remained for a month. The bamboo slats that received the chemical treatment remained for 72 hours in an electric greenhouse (Figure 5) at a temperature of 70 degrees in and then, remained for a month in a natural environment, acquiring an ideal humidity to produce the glued laminated bamboo.

Figure 5: Drying the slats in the greenhouse

Therefore, with the entire treatment process completed, the processing of the slats began, so that they all presented a single pattern, removing their internal and external faces as recommended by Rosa (2013), Rosa et al (2016) and Lima (2013). For this, it was necessary to use a trowel to remove the protuberances of the nodes and flatten the inner face, and a circular saw to finish (Figures 6 and 7). At the end of this process, the slats had a section of 2.8x0.5 cm and was sectioned according to the necessary measurements for the specimens.

Figure 6: Flattening of chemically treated slats

Figure 7: Flattening of naturally treated slats

Gluing the processed slats

After carrying out the entire process of treatment and finishing of the flights, it was followed by gluing for the conformation of the specimens.

In the bonding process, the inner layer must be bonded with the outer layer of the slats, avoiding rupture in the region with lower resistance, in this case the inner layer (ROSA, 2013). According to Moizes (2007), structurally the panels can have one or more layers, with different formats, directions and dispositions of the slats, sheets, or strips. For the mechanical tests and making the prototype, the slats were glued parallel in all layers, so that the seams were mismatched, as it can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Positioning of the slats for gluing

The adhesive selected was a two-component polymer, based on castor beans oil (*mamona* oil), a thermosetting resin. According to Santos, Godinho and Pereira (2017), it is an excellent adhesive alternative because it comes from a renewable source. Castor resin is hardened by mixing components A and B (Figure 9), the proportion being, respectively, 1 to 1^{1/2}, and application to the slats was made with the aid of a brush.

The slats cut according to the necessary measurements for the specimens were glued and pressed with the aid of a manual hydraulic press with a capacity of 15 tons (Figure 10). The glued slats were subjected to a pressure of 1 MPa for a period of 6 hours, according to the work of Lapo and Beraldo (2008).

Figure 9: Castor resin components A and B

Figure 10: Gluing the specimens in the hydraulic press

In total, there were 5 stages of gluing the specimens, where the time, pressure and quantitative variables can be seen in Table 1. In addition, the type of treatment was also a reference for the sequence of gluing the specimens, which allows a comparison on the result of resistance to the detriment of the treatment used.

Table 1: Sample pressing data

Type of slats treatment	Vegetable Polyurethane - Component	Proportion	Quantity	Specimens	Gluing Pressure	Pressing Time
PRESSING 01 – Water + Octoborate	A	1	30 ml	03 specimens (compression) – Board with 16x20x05 cm	1 MPa	6 hours
	B	1 1/2	45 ml			
PRESSING 02 - Water + Octoborate	A	1	10 ml	02 specimens (shear) – Two boards with 8,4x08x05 cm each	1 MPa	6 hours
	B	1 1/2	15 ml			
PRESSING 03 - Water	A	1	25 ml	03 specimens (compression) – Board with 16x20x05 cm	1 MPa	6 hours
	B	1 1/2	37,5 ml			
PRESSING 04 - Water	A	1	10 ml	02 specimens (shear) – Board with 16x8,4x05 cm	1 MPa	6 hours
	B	1 1/2	15 ml			
PRESSING 05 – Water + Octoborate	A	1	10 ml	02 specimens (shear) – Board with 16x8,4x05 cm	1 MPa	6 hours
	B	1 1/2	15 ml			

MECHANICAL TESTS

Considering the dimensions recommended by the ABNT-NBR7190 standard for the specimens, the quantity of slats produced and the equipment available, it was only possible to carry out two tests of mechanical performance: the compression parallel to the fibres and the shear test. on the glue sheet. To make the specimens, the glued plates were cut to form six specimens for the compression test and six for the shear test on the Glue Blade, according to the standard (Figure 11a and Figure 11b, respectively). Three of the specimens for the parallel compression test were made from slats treated with boric acid and borax, the other three with natural treatment. For the shear test, four specimens of chemically treated slats and two with natural treatment were made.

Figure 11a: Compression test specimens

Figure 11b: Specimens for shear testing

Test Results and Comparative Analysis

The compression test parallel to the fibres was performed with the aid of a digital hydraulic press (Figure 14). The loads were applied gradually until the rupture of the specimens.

It was possible to notice that the specimens treated with boric acid and borax in autoclave, three of them, bore a higher load compared to those treated naturally, only by immersion in water, without chemical product. Comparing the best result, of 69.292 Mpa, with the one with the lowest value, 34.78 Mpa, the difference is approximately double the supported load. Another aspect to be observed

is that the specimens chemically treated and in autoclave, even having the same dimensions as those treated naturally, presented higher weights. The values referring to the test can be seen in Table 2.

Figure 12: Compression test parallel to the fibres

Table 2: Compression test data

COMPRESSION PARALLEL TO THE FIBERS					
Specimens	Treatment	Weight (g)	Load (t)	Time (min/s)	MPa
01	Water + Octoborate	298.3	17.665	01:16	69.294
02	Water + Octoborate	308.6	17.313	02:20	67.913
03	Water + Octoborate	289.4	15.872	01:52	62.260
04	Water	238	10.153	02:38	39.827
05	Water	232.5	9.769	02:24	38.320
06	Water	219.7	8.867	02:11	34.78

As for the shear tests of glue lines, due to the lack of a digital hydraulic press suitable for this test in our laboratory, it was necessary to develop a metallic part to correctly press the area defined by the standard followed. Thus, the test was carried out with the aid of a manual hydraulic press to apply the load until failure (Figure 13). The values of resistance in the glue sheet, regardless of the type of treatment, did not vary so sharply, since the highest, 8.3 Mpa, and the lowest result, 4.6 Mpa, resulted from specimens with the same treatment. It is important to note that all six specimens broke in the bamboo and not in the glue sheet (Figure 16), which according to Lapo and Beraldo (2008), is characteristic of a structural connection. This reinforces the efficiency of castor resin as an adhesive for glued laminated bamboo. The test data can be seen in Table 3.

Comparing the values obtained by other authors, who also used the NBR7190 as a reference, it can be noted that the average loads achieved in this work are very close to the results obtained in the works that served as a reference (Table 4). It is noteworthy that the average value considered in the compression test for comparative analysis was that obtained from the weighting of the values reached with the specimens chemically treated in autoclave, which presented discrepant results in relation to those treated only with water.

Figure 13: Shear tests of glue lines

Figure 14: Shear specimens with rupture in bamboo

Table 3: Shear test data on the glue lines
SHEAR STRENGTH IN THE GLUE LINE

Specimens	Treatment	MPa	Load (t)	Time (s)
01	Water + Octoborate	4.6	1.146	29
02	Water + Octoborate	7.73	1.933	37
03	Water + Octoborate	5.7	1.425	31
04	Water + Octoborate	8.3	2.074	42
05	Water	7.11	1.778	50
06	Water	7.24	1.810	33

Table 4: Comparison of results with other authors

Research with (GluLam) bamboo	Compression parallel to the fibers (MPa)	Shear on the glue lamina (MPa)
Results of this search	66,48	6,78
Gonçalves et al (2000)	55	10
Lima (2013)	100,9 e 97,6	5,1 e 8,1
Lapo e Beraldo (2008)	42,6 a 72,4	6 a 17 MPa
Boogard (2016)	57,61	-

Furthermore, it should be noted that, among the authors selected for this comparison, only Lapo and Beraldo (2008) also used castor oil resin as an adhesive. Researchers Rivero (2003), Boogard (2016) and Lima (2013) applied PVA-based adhesives and a resin called Cascophen. We also emphasize that the different bonding methods, some dimensions of the specimens that were adapted by some authors, types of treatment and bamboo species used, may be factors that differentiated the results achieved.

PARTITION WALL DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE EXECUTION

The research had as its final goal the elaboration of the project and prototype of a delimiter of the architectural space using as constructive material the glued laminated bamboo. This propositional stage was preceded by the study of projects and reference works that used glued laminated bamboo as constructive and expressive material in sealing or even structural elements.

Among the works researched, we highlight the residence of designer Osiris Hertman (Figure 13), located in a Dutch nature reserve, in which the Glued Laminated Bamboo (GLB) was used as elements for the facade cladding. In the case of outdoor application, the solid bamboo boards undergo a treatment process that increases stability, density, and hardness, consequently having greater durability and fire resistance, which can last up to 25 years, according to the manufacturers.

Figure 15: Residence of Osiris Hertman. Source: www.moso-bamboo.com

Bamboo structures are light and resistant, in addition to all the advantages of being a material considered by many to be the most ecological. And as can be seen, it can be used in different ways as a sealing element, and other suitable products. Considering this panorama on the use of glued laminated bamboo and given the broad feasibility of the product design, we sought to explore a proposal for an architectural element that had the function of delimiting the architectural space, but without blocking the entry of light or ventilation.

One of the concepts used in the design of the partition was modularization, important for the manufacturing and assembly process, without losing sight of more aesthetically expressive arrangements.

Some designs of partition components were analysed in order to direct ideas on how to work the modules, even if they were not built with glued laminated bamboo. Among the components of partitions studied, the following stand out: the mortise louvers of Casa Kimball, developed by Rangr Studio in 2009, in the Dominican Republic (Figure 16); the wooden louvers structured on metal rods, from the 2017 project The Abacus House, by StudioXS, located in Bangalore (Figure 17).

Figure 16: Stone *Briese*, Kimball House. Source: www.ranger.com

Figure 17: The Abacus House. Fonte: www.archdaily.com

Therefore, five proposals for partitions were made with the help of Trimble's Sketchup program, to select the one that best met the production and assembly requirements using glued laminated bamboo, also considering the limitations of machinery in our research laboratory. Such proposals for partitions composed of BLC boards can be observed below: Proposal 1 – In the form of flights (vertical or horizontal), with straight or rounded ends, with repetition of elements and structured with metal rods; Proposal 2 – Plug-in modules from BLC boards; Proposal 3 – Plug-in modules for two types of components (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Proposals for bamboo partitions designed by scholarship student Kauan Silva

Proposal 2 proved to be more relevant, since, with the plug-in plates, it does not need other materials for its structuring. This aspect adds to the sustainable value of bamboo, in addition to the expressiveness of the elaborate form. Thus, in the development of the proposal, we sought to work with modular fitting elements, with plates sized at 18x18x1.5 centimeters (height, width, and

thickness, respectively). The fitting, in addition to reducing the use of other materials for the conformation of the partition, also allows greater flexibility in the arrangement in space (Figure 19). In total, 4 different parts constitute the sealing element developed: a bar at the top and bottom, with a 5x5 cm section and 70 cm length, with 2 holes for fixing to the floor and ceiling with 5.0x70 phillips flat head screws millimeters; a metallic support of center 1329, generally used for fixing glass to the floor or wall, with the function of fixing the plates to the bars attached to the floor and ceiling; and two types of 18x18x1.5 cm boards, called board A (with 30 degree tears at the top and bottom) and board B (with 30 degree tears at the top and “U” shaped cut-out in the lower central part). Such cutouts provided a staggered arrangement in the sealing panel. The details of plates A and B, and the plate fitting scheme can be seen in Figure 20a and Figure 20b.

Figure 19: The proposal bamboo partitions developed by scholarship student Kauan Silva.

Figure 20a: Details of plates A and B

Figure 20b: Plates fitting scheme

The last step of this research was the manufacture of the prototype of the GLB boards that make up the proposed partition. The technique of pressing the bamboo slats and making them followed the same steps used in the manufacture of the specimens for the mechanical tests, with the aid of a hydraulic press and the use of castor oil resin as an adhesive. For each slab, 21 slats with 2.8x1.5 cm sections were needed, distributed in 3 layers, which resulted in the production of 5 slabs of 18x18x15 cm, a quantity limited by the number of slats already extracted from the stems and processed. Finally, the necessary cuts were made in the plates for the fittings, both for the metallic supports and among themselves. The result can be seen in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Final prototype produced

FINAL REMARKS

From the theoretical basis raised on the subject studied, it was possible to produce BLC panels using a biodegradable adhesive, castor resin. Regarding the types of treatment, immersion in water with boric acid and borax was one of the most recommended by the authors and being used in conjunction with an autoclave followed by drying in an oven considerably accelerates the process. Such treatment, in addition to providing better protection against attacks by xylophagous organisms, seems to have provided greater resistance to compressive stress, in view of the most outstanding results of the specimens treated in this way. Furthermore, the chosen species (*Dendrocalamus Asper*) proved to be adequate, since, as it has a thicker wall, it facilitates the removal of slats.

Initially realizing two mechanical performance tests to analyse the resistance to compression and shear forces in the glue sheet, a very satisfactory result was obtained, when compared to another research already carried out. However, it was not possible to perform all the mechanical tests established by NBR7190 standard due to the limitations of the equipment available in the laboratory of our university (LABEME/UFPB), which can be developed in future works.

Despite this limitation, it is important to emphasize that the extraction of the plant, treatment, and the entire process of making the prototype were carried out by the members of the research group in our state.

Furthermore, it was possible to perceive that the GLB further expands the potential of using bamboo as an expressive material and an eco-responsible architectural technical solution.

The modularized proposal of a space delimiter exemplified a feasible way of using the benefited slats. However, more specific equipment to produce GLB, which already exists in countries with the most developed technical bamboo culture, are necessary for large-scale production.

Research and experiments on bamboo lamination by industrial process in the academic environment, constitute an important factor to boost the industrialization of Glued Laminated Bamboo (GLB) in Brazil, as has been carried out by some universities located in the centre-south of the country, being able to compose panels of reconstituted wood due to its excellent mechanical resistance.

Research with GLB and even bamboo agglomerate (already started by the research group TEKTONIK.AS) needs to be continued given its environmental, economic, and social importance, however, we need better infrastructure in our laboratories, with more equipment and technical personnel and, mainly, from the government incentive to the bamboo production chain in the state of Paraíba, which could increase the bioeconomy sector in that state.

Considering the importance of sealing systems for the architectural form and delimitation of its spaces, as well as the environmental impact caused by conventional masonry systems, structural elements, floors and roofs, the investigation on glued laminated bamboo as a renewable and expressive material in these systems need to be deepened. Besides, in our country, engineered bamboo standards need to

be implemented to encourage the use of bamboo in the construction industry and to increase the bioeconomy sector on our planet.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.